

Figure S1

Examples of defense-rich plasmids

Examples of defense-dense plasmids

Figure S2

Figure S3

Figure S4

Figure S6

Figure S7

Figure S8

Antimicrobial resistance class

Antimicrobial resistance class

Antimicrobial resistance type

Antimicrobial resistance type

Figure S10

Figure S11

Figure S12

Number of defense systems

Number of AMR genes

Number of anti-defense systems

Host Phylum

- Acidobacteriota
- Actinomycetota
- Ascomycota
- Bacillota
- Bacteroidota
- Campylobacterota
- Candidatus Absconditabacteria
- Candidatus Binatota
- Candidatus Melainabacteria
- Candidatus Omnitrophota
- Candidatus Saccharibacteria
- Chlamydiota
- Cyanobacteriota
- Deinococcota
- Euryarchaeota
- Fusobacteriota
- Kiritimatiellota
- Lentisphaerota
- Mycoplasmatota
- Nitrososphaerota
- Pseudomonadota
- Spirochaetota
- Synergistota
- Thermodesulfobacteriota
- Verrucomicrobiota

Predicted mobility

Ecosystem category

- Air
- Algae
- Amphibia
- Annelida
- Aquatic
- Arthropoda, Terrestrial
- Arthropoda: Chelicerates
- Arthropoda: Crustaceans
- Arthropoda: Hemiptera
- Arthropoda: Insects
- Artificial ecosystem
- Bioreactor
- Bioremediation
- Biotransformation
- Birds
- Built environment
- Cephalochordata
- Cnidaria
- Echinodermata
- Fish
- Food production
- Fungi
- Industrial production
- Invertebrates
- Lab enrichment
- Mammals
- Mammals: Human
- Microbial
- Modeled
- Mollusca
- Nematoda
- Plants
- Porifera
- Protists
- Reptilia
- Sewage treatment plant
- Solid waste
- Terrestrial
- Tunicates
- Unclassified
- Wastewater
- WWTP
- Missing

Figure S13

